

Tsallis Entropy and a Conservation of Energy Scheme Part 3

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In Part I, we argued that if one considers elastic two body scattering: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ with $G(f(e_1)G(f(e_2))) = G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4))$ for time reversal balance, then if $d \ln(G(f)) = f^{\text{power } -q} df$, one obtains the Tsallis $\ln_q(f) = (f^{\text{power } (1-q)} - 1) / (1-q)$ (where for $q=1$ $\ln_q(f) = \ln(f)$) as given in (1). Furthermore, (1) writes: Tsallis Entropy = Sum over i $f_i^{\text{power } q} \ln_q(f_i)$ and in Part 2, we argued that $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ has the physical meaning of q trials of a particle with e_i being necessary to produce one reaction, i.e.. AND scenario.

In this note, we consider the factor $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ and the relation $d \ln(G(f)) = f^{\text{power } -q} df$ and note that their product is df , which when integrated yields 0. A similar result holds for Shannon's entropy, i.e. $d \ln(f) = df/f$ so $f df/f = df$. We suggest in this note, that according to the formalism used, $\ln(G(f))$ is taken to be equivalent to $-e_i/T$. Thus, when extremizing entropy $\sum P(f_i) \ln(G(f_i))$ one has two terms: $dP(f) \ln(G(f))$ and $P(f) d \ln(G(f))$. We suggest, as a principle, that the second should be a constant multiplied by df in order that $\int df = 0$ because both $\ln(G(f))$ and a modified function: $\ln(G(f)) + d \ln(G(f))$ should both be linked to $-e_i/T$ so that $\sum P(f_i) \ln(G(f_i)) = \sum P(f_i) \{ \ln(G(f_i)) + d \ln(G(f_i)) \}$ meaning that $\sum P(f_i) d \ln(G(f_i)) = 0$. This suggests that $d \ln(G(f_i)) = \text{constant } df_i$ because $\sum df_i = 0$. In other words, modifying $B = \ln(G)$ from its equilibrium result cannot break the relation of new B still being equivalent to $-e_i/T$.

We consider this idea for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases and the Tsallis scenario. We point out that if this is the case, then given $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ has the probability for a reaction with e_i to occur, then one may automatically set $d \ln(G(f)) = f^{\text{power } -q} df$ and obtain the Tsallis entropy from the single assumption of $P(f) = f^{\text{power } q}$, which is based on a physical interpretation.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

If one considers reaction balance with time reversal for elastic two body scattering, then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

This implies that: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (where $-1/T$ is a constant). We argue that this is an important result because $\ln(f(e_i))$ is associated with a conserved quantity. We suggest that this result appears naturally in maximization of entropy subject to an average energy constraint, but is already anticipated from ((1b)). We also note that:

df/f is the form obtained by taking the differential of ((1b)) and dividing by the function itself. We observe that:

$$f df/f = df \quad \text{such that} \quad \int df = 0 \quad ((2))$$

We consider ((2)), namely that probabilities involved a formulation of entropy yield df when multiplied by the differential of the probability appearing in ((1b)) as a principle. In general, one does not have a simple result like $f(e_i)$ as in ((1b)), but $G(f(e_i))$, where G is a more complicated expression. Then:

$$\ln(G(f(e_i))) = -e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

Forming the entropy, however, is not always so simple as using $f(e_i) \ln(G(f(e_i)))$ or even $P(f(e_i) \ln(G(f(e_i))))$ as will be seen in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. The key point we wish to make is that entropic term (or terms) consist of a probability type term multiplied by an information type term in the MB, FD, BE and Tsallis cases and that the differential of the information term(s) multiplied by the probability terms should yield df which integrates to 0.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

For these cases, ((1b)) is replaced with:

$$G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((4))$$

where $\ln(G(f(e_i))) = -e_i/T$. ((5a))

Here $G(f(e_i)) = f(e_i) / \{ 1 -/+ f(e_i) \}$ ((5b)) where $-$ applies to the FD case and $+$ to the BE.

The entropy for the FD case is:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ f \ln(f_i) + (1-f_i) \ln(1-f_i) \quad ((6))$$

One may see that one has two different pieces of information, each associated with its own probability, i.e. f and $1-f$. One does not have the simple case of $P(f) \ln(G(f))$. Nevertheless, given that $\ln(G)$ is linked with $-e_i/T$ one again expects that the differential of the information pieces multiplied by the respective probability pieces should yield constant df which integrates to 0 or 0 itself. Applying this idea to ((6)) one has:

$$f \, d \ln f + (1-f) \, d \ln(1-f) = 0 \, df \quad ((7))$$

Thus, in the MB case, one had $f \, d \ln f = df$ which integrates to 0, but in the FD case one has 0. For the BE case, one has:

Entropy = Sum over $i \ f_i \ln(f_i) - (1+f_i) \ln(1+f_i)$ and again the result ((7)).

Thus, there is something special about the variation of the information expression which is then multiplied by a probability. Due to conservation of energy this term is either df or 0 in the MB, FD and BE cases. We suggest that the same result should hold in the Tsallis case and argues that this might allow one to obtain the Tsallis scenario based on one physical assumption, namely

that instead of $f(e_i)$ representing the probability for an e_i to react, one uses $f(e_i)$ power q , i.e. one needs q AND situations to obtain one successful reaction

Tsallis Case

We suggest that the above ideas and the single assumption:

Probability for an e_i to react = $f(e_i)$ power q ((8))

lead to Tsallis entropy.

Here $f(e_i)$ is the probability to find an e_i , but the presence of a single e_i does not guarantee a reaction. Rather one needs on average q tries to get one e_i reaction, or the presence of q e_i 's in one place for one to react.

The ideas above suggest that $d \ln(G(f_i))$ multiplied by an appropriate probability (or split into two pieces for the FD and BE cases) should yield df or 0. Given that there is only one probability, f_i power q , we suggest one seeks: constant df . Thus:

f_i power q $d \ln(G(f_i)) = \text{constant } df \rightarrow d \ln(G(f_i)) = f_i$ power $-q$ df ((9))

Integrating ((9)) yields $\ln q(f_i) = (f_i \text{ power } (1-q) - 1)/(1-q)$ ((10))

and Tsallis entropy is: $\text{Sum over } i P(f_i) \ln(G(f_i)) = \text{Sum over } i f_i \text{ power } q (f_i \text{ power } (1-q) - 1)/(1-q)$

((10)) in keeping with the form of (1).

Maximization of Entropy Subject to a Constraint

In the above Tsallis case, we used $P(f_i) = f_i$ power q in keeping with the form used in (1). This suggests that if one wishes to use Tsallis entropy $P(f_i) \ln(G(f_i))$ then the constraint to use is: $\text{Sum over } i e_i P(f_i)$ and not $\text{Sum over } i e_i f_i$ (used in the MB, FD and BE cases). In other words, there is a constant energy associated only with successful interaction results, which create thermal equilibrium in the first place.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there seems to be a general principle linked with conservation of energy in two body scattering. In particular, if: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4))$ then $d \ln(G(f(e_i))) = \text{function}(f(e_i)) df_i$ such that an associated probability $P(f(e_i))$ yields: $P(f(e_i)) d \ln(G(f(e_i))) = \text{constant } df_i$, with $\text{Sum over } i df_i = 0$. This idea holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein and Tsallis cases. Moreover, we argue that using one physical assumption, $P(f_i) = f_i$ power q , and the above principle, one may obtain the explicit form of Tsallis entropy. $P(f_i) = f_i$ power q suggests that one requires q instances of e_i

(AND situation) in order for one reaction involving e_i to occur. Thus, this single physical scenario leads to the Tsallis form if one uses the principle $P(f(e_i)) d\ln G(f(e_i)) = \text{constant } df_i$, we argue.

References

1. Okamura, K. Emergent Families of Tsallis Entropies from the q -deformed combinatorics (Sept. 28, 2024) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2407.11257>